

Heat transfer in conductors of cylindrical cross-section with diffusive boundary scattering

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We present a theoretical study of heat transfer properties in three-dimensional cylindrical conductors of finite lengths in the ballistic regime of phonon propagation. The phonon emission is considered to be radiative and its interactions with the lateral boundary is assumed to be completely diffusive. The main goal of this study is to determine the temperature profile and the features of its formation for the generalized case of a conductor of finite length. A matrix numerical solution of the integral equation for the particle energy flux is obtained and an approximate analytical solution of this equation is proposed. The heat flux and thermal conductivity coefficient are determined; and the significant difference between our results and those of the generally accepted formulation in the Knudsen regime and the Casimir model is discussed.

Keywords: heat transfer, conductor, thermal conductivity, ballistic regime of phonon propagation, phonon emission.

Introduction

Thermal transfer in the ballistic regime of phonon propagation has regained interest with the need to understand the thermal properties of nanostructures and solids at sufficiently low temperatures or dimensions where the interaction between the heat carriers can be neglected. In this regime, the thermal resistance of a conductor is determined by the reflective properties of the lateral walls of the conductor. The most known problem in this field is the determination of heat fluxes and temperature profiles along conductors under diffuse boundary conditions, that is when a phonon incident on the lateral wall of a conductor is reflected from it with equal probability in all directions. Under such a formulation, phonon motion becomes equivalent to the motion of rarefied gas in the Knudsen regime [1] with the approximation of complete accommodation of particles upon reflection at the boundary.

For phonons, such an analogous treatment was first considered by Casimir [2], who pointed-out the equivalence between the flow of classical particles under the action of a pressure gradient and the motion of phonons under a temperature gradient. In Refs. 1 and 2, it was assumed that

external sources create a gradient of the driving force (pressure or temperature), and the length of the conductor was formally considered infinite.

Following the works of Knudsen [1], the motion of rarefied gas under the influence of a pressure difference between the ends of a pipe of finite length was solved by Clausius [3]. He found an integral equation that described the coordinate dependence of the particle flux at the lateral boundary. The same equation was used to study heat flows in a cylindrical conductor [4, 5], with mixed specular and diffuse reflections of phonons from the lateral boundary, as well as in two-dimensional nanostructures for the case of purely diffuse reflections [6]. In those works, numerical iterative methods for solving integral equations were used.

In this work, we study heat transfer properties in three-dimensional cylindrical conductors of finite lengths in the ballistic regime of phonon propagation. We propose a simpler matrix approach for solving such integral equations and an analytical approximated solution. Our approach is therefore a generalization of the Knudsen and Casimir models to cylindrical conductors of finite lengths. It can also be generalized to different cross-sections of the conductor and include partially specular reflection from the lateral boundary.

Setting-up of the integral equation and its solution

Let us recall the derivation of the original integral equation for the temperature distribution along the lateral boundaries of the cylindrical conductor. In the three-dimensional case, when the boundaries are surfaces, the flow of particles between two emitting, absorbing, or reflecting infinitesimal surface elements is given by the known relation [7]:

$$F_{12} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{(\mathbf{n}_1 \mathbf{r}_{12})(\mathbf{n}_2 \mathbf{r}_{21})}{r_{12}^4} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2}{r_{12}^2}. \quad (1)$$

Here, \mathbf{n}_1 and \mathbf{n}_2 are the normal unit vectors to these surface elements, \mathbf{r}_{12} is the vector from one element to the other; the value π determines the normalization. This relation describes the isotropic angular distribution of emitting particles (Lambert law), and for reflected particles, it describes complete accommodation [8].

Since its formulation in Ref. 1, relation (1) has been widely used to describe the Knudsen effect and particle flows in rarefied classical gases, as well as to study radiative heat transfer in phonon systems of solids [2].

The pioneering results of Knudsen [1], who proposed the idea of describing particle flows in the ballistic regime in infinitely long pipes, were generalized by Clausing [3], who considered the problem of transferring rarefied gas through pipes of finite length. Clausing proposed an integral equation that can be written in the following generalized form:

$$\Psi_e(\mathbf{r}_e) = \int_{S_{\text{heater}}} F(\mathbf{r}_h, \mathbf{r}_e) \Psi_{\text{heater}}(\mathbf{r}_h) d\mathbf{r}_h + \int_{S_{\text{cooler}}} F(\mathbf{r}_c, \mathbf{r}_e) \Psi_{\text{cooler}}(\mathbf{r}_c) d\mathbf{r}_c + \int_{S_{\text{edge}}} d\mathbf{r}'_e \Psi_e(\mathbf{r}'_e) F(\mathbf{r}'_e, \mathbf{r}_e). \quad (2a)$$

This expression describes the energy flux of incident (and reflecting) particles $\Psi_e(\mathbf{r}_e)$ at a given location \mathbf{r}_e on the lateral surface. The first term corresponds to phonons that radiate from the heater with the energy flux $\Psi_{\text{heater}}(\mathbf{r}_h)$ and go to a given point on the lateral surface without reflections. The second term corresponds to phonons that are directed to this point directly from the cooler, which radiates phonons with the energy flux $\Psi_{\text{cooler}}(\mathbf{r}_c)$. Assuming that the radiation from the surfaces of the heater and cooler are uniform, these functions can be considered as constants $\Psi_{\text{heater}}(\mathbf{r}_h) = \Psi_{\text{heater}}$ and $\Psi_{\text{cooler}}(\mathbf{r}_c) = \Psi_{\text{cooler}}$ and can be taken out of the integration sign. For classical particles, the external fluxes are determined by the pressure and temperature of the source using the Maxwell distribution, and for thermal phonon systems by the temperature using the Planck blackbody radiation formula.

The third term in Eq. (2a) describes phonons that have already been reflected one or more times from the lateral boundaries. Due to the cylindrical symmetry of the problem, their energy flux density depends only on the longitudinal

coordinate $\Psi_e(\mathbf{r}_e) = \Psi_e(x)$. For the same reason, the functions F also have a simpler form: $F(\mathbf{r}_h, \mathbf{r}_e) = F(\mathbf{r}_h, x)$, $F(\mathbf{r}_c, \mathbf{r}_e) = F(\mathbf{r}_c, x)$, and $F(\mathbf{r}'_e, \mathbf{r}_e) = F(x', x)$.

Then, for simplicity, following to Refs. 3–5, we shifted and normalized all of the particle energy fluxes by expression $\Phi = (\Psi - \Psi_{\text{cooler}}) / (\Psi_{\text{heater}} - \Psi_{\text{cooler}})$. Under this notation, the energy flux from the heater turns to be equal to unity $\Phi_{\text{heater}} = 1$, the heat flux of the cooler becomes equal to zero $\Phi_{\text{cooler}} = 0$, and the heat flux of reflected (incident) phonons at the definite point of the lateral boundary is defined by expression $\Phi(x) = (\Psi_e(x) - \Psi_{\text{cooler}}) / (\Psi_{\text{heater}} - \Psi_{\text{cooler}})$.

For functions redefined in this way, the integral relation (2a) becomes the following:

$$\Phi(x) = \int_{S_{\text{source}}} F(\mathbf{r}_s, x) d\mathbf{r}_s + \int_{S_{\text{edge}}} d\mathbf{r}_e \Phi(\mathbf{r}_e) F(\mathbf{r}_e, x). \quad (2b)$$

The first term in Eq. (2b) determines the flow of particles that comes to a given point on the lateral surface of the cross-section with coordinate x from the entire area of the source S_{source} . The second term describes the particles that fall at a given point on the lateral surface with the longitudinal coordinate x from the points of the surface element located on the perimeter of the cross-section of the conductor, which is located at coordinate x_1 .

In particular, for a cylindrical sample of finite length L and diameter D , Eq. (2b) takes the following form [3]:

$$\Phi(X) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1+2X^2}{\sqrt{1+X^2}} - 2X \right\} + \int_0^{L/d} dX_1 \left\{ 1 - |X - X_1| \frac{2(X - X_1)^2 + 3}{2(1 + (X - X_1)^2)^{3/2}} \right\} \Phi(X_1). \quad (3)$$

Here, the coordinate x is normalized to the diameter of the cylindrical conductor $X = x/D$. The heater has the coordinate $x = 0$ and cooler coordinate is $x = L$.

When studying heat flows of quasiparticles, thermal thermostats are considered as reservoirs providing a constant temperature of the heater and cooler at the ends of the sample [4, 5]. For flat samples, such as nanoribbons or nanofilms, the corresponding equation was derived in [6].

Equation (3) belongs to the family of Fredholm integral equations of the second kind [9] and we have to solve it numerically by using an iterative or matrix method. The advantage of the iterative method, which is described in detail in Ref. 6, is that consecutive iteration corresponds to the consecutive reflection of a phonon from the side wall. This makes it possible to determine the full path length of a phonon inside a conductor. The disadvantages of iterative methods include long convergence times, especially in the case of long and narrow conductors [10].

The matrix technique, which is quite standard for solving such integral equations, immediately gives the final desired

result but does not allow one to determine the features of the motion of particles inside a conductor or to generalize solutions to the case of taking into account possible specular reflection or scattering of particles inside conductors.

Moreover, for long and thin conductors the problem of error accumulation arises, so the results are not accurate enough and additional methods must be used to obtain the correct results. In this paper, we will apply the approximate analytical method together with the matrix method and show that their simultaneous use allows us to obtain the results with the desired degree of accuracy.

To apply the matrix method, we change the normalization of the longitudinal coordinate x from a normalization with respect to the transverse size (diameter) $X = x/D$ to a normalization with respect to the longitudinal size $\tilde{X} = x/L$, that is, to the length of the conductor L . Formally, we consider conductors of unit length, but of different diameters. In longitudinal variables normalized to the length of the conductor, the integral Eq. (3) takes the form

$$\Phi(\tilde{X}) = g(\tilde{X}) + \int_0^1 h(\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X})\Phi(\tilde{X}_1)d\tilde{X}_1, \quad (4)$$

where the inhomogeneity has the form

$$g_{\text{Cyl}}(\tilde{X}) = \frac{1}{d} \left\{ \frac{\tilde{X}^2 + d^2/2}{\sqrt{\tilde{X}^2 + d^2}} - \tilde{X} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where $d = D/L$, and kernel

$$h_{\text{Cyl}}(\tilde{X}) = \frac{1}{d} \left\{ 1 - |\tilde{X}| \frac{\tilde{X}^2 + 3d^2/2}{(\tilde{X}^2 + d^2)^{3/2}} \right\}. \quad (6)$$

Next, the conductor area was divided into a certain number N of cells with coordinates $\tilde{X}_n = n/N$, $n = 1, \dots, N$. Then, from Eq. (4), we obtain a system of linear equations for the values $\Phi_n = \Phi(\tilde{X}_n)$ of the normalized parameter that determines the particle flux density in each cell:

$$\Phi_n = g_n + \sum_{m=1}^{m=N} h_{nm}\Phi_m. \quad (7)$$

Here, the vector of inhomogeneity and matrix coefficients are determined by the relation $g_n = g(\tilde{X}_n)$ and $h_{nm} = h(\tilde{X}_m - \tilde{X}_n) = h(|\tilde{X}_m - \tilde{X}_n|)$.

A complete solution is reduced to solving a system of linear Eqs. (7), which allows us to obtain results for the flux profile for conductors of different ratios of length to diameter. An example of obtained results for the flux profile for some ratios of the length L to transverse size (diameter D) is presented in Fig. 1. The obtained graphic displays the well-known result that the dependence of the energy flux of particles falling on the side wall at a given location is practically a linear function. This function is quasi-hori-

Fig. 1. The energy flux profile in cylindrical conductors for some diameter-to-length ratios indicated in the figure.

zontal for short and wide conductors and has a maximum (almost unit) slope for long narrow conductors.

This behavior allows us to consider the following linear approximation for the analytical description of the coordinate dependence of the value $\Phi(\tilde{X})$:

$$\Phi_{\text{linear}}(\tilde{X}) = \frac{1}{2} + \Delta\Phi(L, D) \left[\frac{1}{2} - \tilde{X} \right] \quad (8)$$

with a coefficient $\Delta\Phi(L, D)$ that turns out to be a function of the dimensions of the conductor.

This approximation at first was proposed by Clausing [3] for the study of rarefied gases in tubes, and in Ref. 10, we used it for the study of heat flows in two-dimensional nanostructures.

Thus, if we are looking for a solution of Eq. (4) in the form Eq. (8), the problem is reduced to finding the difference $\Delta\Phi(L, D)$ of the energy flux at the ends of the conductor. In the work of Clausing [3], various proposals for choosing this value were discussed, such as, for example, minimizing the deviation of the numerical solution and the analytical one along the entire length of the conductor. In Ref. 10, it was proposed to find the coefficient $\Delta\Phi(L, D)$ in such a way that function (8) corresponds exactly to the solution of the integral Eq. (4) at the ends of the conductor. That is,

$$\Phi_{\text{linear}}(\tilde{X} = 0) = g(\tilde{X} = 0) + \int_0^1 h(\tilde{X}_1)\Phi_{\text{linear}}(\tilde{X}_1)d\tilde{X}_1 \quad (9)$$

and

$$\Phi_{\text{linear}}(\tilde{X} = 1) = g(\tilde{X} = 1) + \int_0^1 h(\tilde{X}_1 - 1)\Phi_{\text{linear}}(\tilde{X}_1)d\tilde{X}_1. \quad (10)$$

Due to the symmetry of the solution $\Phi(\tilde{X}) = 1 - \Phi(1 - \tilde{X})$ relative to the middle of the conductor, these two conditions do not contradict each other and are sufficient to determine the coefficient $\Delta\Phi(L, D)$.

Fig. 2. (a) The dependence of difference $\Delta\Phi(L,D)$ on the ratio of diameter to the length of the cylindrical conductor. Points represent the results of numerical calculation of Eq. (7) and the line refers to the calculation by Eq. (12). (b) The difference between analytical approximation $\Delta\Phi_a$ [Eq. (12)] and value $\Delta\Phi_n$ resulting from numerical calculation by Eq. (7) as a function of diameter-to-length ratio.

Let us recall that in Ref. 11 for the 2D case, the following simple analytical expression was obtained for the energy flux difference $\Delta\Phi(L,D)$ at the ends of the nanoribbon:

$$\Delta\Phi(L,W) = \left(1 + \frac{4W}{L} \frac{\sqrt{L^2 + W^2}}{L + W + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}} \right)^{-1}, \quad (11)$$

where W is the width of the 2D conductor.

In the case of a cylindrical conductor, from Eqs. (9) and (10), we get a slightly more cumbersome expression for this difference:

$$\Delta\Phi(L,D) = \left(1 + 2D \frac{\sqrt{D^2 + L^2} \left\{ (D+2L)\sqrt{D^2 + L^2} + (D^2 + 2L^2) \right\}}{L(4D^2 + LD + 4L^2)(L + \sqrt{D^2 + L^2})} \right)^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

Despite its cumbersomeness, it is valid with some degree of accuracy for arbitrary ratios of the length of a cylindrical conductor to its diameter and generalizes other approximations made for the coefficients $\Delta\Phi(L,D)$ by other authors, beginning with the works of Clausing [3].

Figure 2(a) shows a comparison of the value $\Delta\Phi(L,D)$ found by the numerical calculations using Eq. (7) and given by the approximate analytical expression (8) for different values of the diameter-to-length ratio D/L . The difference between these values is shown in Fig. 2(b) and from the figure, we can see that the difference between the analytical expression and the numerical calculations does not exceed $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$. This result allows us to use an explicit expression for the energy flux profile $\Phi(\tilde{X})$ [Eq. (7)] for the study of the thermal transport properties of cylindrical conductors in the next section.

Heat flow in a cylindrical conductor

Equation (8) found for the particle energy flux $\Phi(\tilde{X})$ at each point of the conductor surface allows us to determine

the net heat flux that is transferred by heat carriers (phonons) from the heater to the cooler, both directly and after reflections from the walls. To begin with, it is necessary to determine the heat flux of those phonons that, after reflection from the side walls, return to the heater and are absorbed by it:

$$Q_h = \int_0^L g(\tilde{X})\Phi(\tilde{X})dA(x) = P \int_0^L g(\tilde{X})\Phi(\tilde{X})dx. \quad (13)$$

Here, A is the cross-sectional area at point x , and P is the perimeter of the cross-section at point x . From this, we obtain for the flux density

$$q_h = \frac{Q_h}{A} = \frac{P}{A} \int_0^L g(\tilde{X})\Phi(\tilde{X})dx = \frac{4}{D} \int_0^L g(\tilde{X})\Phi(\tilde{X})dx. \quad (14)$$

Using the conservation law, we get the total heat flux that goes to the sink (cooler)

$$q_c = 1 - q_h = 1 - \frac{4}{D} \int_0^L g(\tilde{X})\Phi(\tilde{X})dx. \quad (15)$$

Now, we can use the analytical Eqs. (8) and (15) and get the explicit expression for heat flux and, hence, for the coefficient of thermal conductance

$$q_c(L,D) = 1 - \frac{1 + \Delta\Phi(L,D)}{2} Q_0(L,D) + \frac{\Delta\Phi(L,D)}{L} Q_1(L,D). \quad (16)$$

Here,

$$Q_0(L,D) = \frac{2}{D^2} L \left(\sqrt{D^2 + L^2} - L \right) \quad (17)$$

and

$$Q_1(L,D) = \frac{4}{3D^2} \left\{ (D^2 + L^2)^{3/2} - D^3 - \frac{3}{2} D^2 \left(\sqrt{D^2 + L^2} - D \right) - L^3 \right\}. \quad (18)$$

The obtained general Eq. (16) gives the well-known classical result of Knudsen and Casimir [1, 2] in the case when the temperature gradient on the walls of the conductors is specified by external sources, that is $\Delta\Phi(L, D) = 1$, and when the conductor is located symmetrically relative to the point $x = 0$, that is

$$\Phi_{\text{Knudsen}}(\tilde{X}) = 1 - \tilde{X}, \quad -1 < \tilde{X} < 1. \quad (19)$$

In this case, from Eqs. (15) and (19), or directly from Eq. (16) we obtain

$$Q_{\text{grad}}(L, D) = 2(1 - Q_0(L, D)) + \frac{2}{L} Q_1(L, D) \quad (20)$$

or

$$Q_{\text{grad}}(L, D) = 2 \left(1 - \frac{2}{D^2} L \left(\sqrt{D^2 + L^2} - L \right) + \frac{1}{L} \frac{4}{3D^2} \left\{ (D^2 + L^2)^{3/2} - D^3 - \frac{3}{2} D^2 \left(\sqrt{D^2 + L^2} - D \right) - L^3 \right\} \right).$$

Now, we are letting the length L of the conductor tend to infinity, we obtain the classical known result [1] for the normalized flow in a cylindrical conductor:

$$Q_{\text{Knudsen}}(L, D) = \frac{4D}{3L}. \quad (21)$$

In the general case of conductors of a given finite length, the expression for the heat flux [Eq. (16)] turns out to be more complex and differs significantly from expression (21) when the length and diameter of the conductor are of the same order.

Figure 3 shows a comparison of the results of the numerical calculation and the analytical result for the heat flow

Fig. 3. Dependence of the normalized heat flux Eq. (15) in a cylindrical conductor on the length-to-diameter ratio L/D . The points correspond to the results of the exact numerical solution of the original Eq. (4), the solid line is the analytical dependence [Eq. (16)], and the dashed line is the classical dependence [Eq. (21)] in the Knudsen model [1].

through cylindrical conductors with different diameter-to-length ratios. It is evident from the figure that the analytical formula Eq. (16) corresponds quite well to the results of the exact numerical solution of the integral Eq. (4) in a large range of conductor diameter-to-length ratios.

The figure also shows the dependence determined by the classical formula [Eq. (21)]. It is evident from the figure that this dependence approaches our exact solution [Eq. (16)] with increasing conductor length, but still differs from it by 12%, even when the ratio $L/D = 100$.

Conclusion

We have studied the heat transport properties of cylindrical dielectric thermal conductors in the ballistic regime of phonon propagation with completely diffusive reflection of phonons from the lateral walls. In this case, the necessary condition is that the phonon wavelength be much less than the size of the conductor, that is, its diameter. For this reason, the proposed model may not be applicable at very low temperatures and for very narrow nanowires.

Within the framework of the proposed model, the integral equation that described the phonon energy flux at definite points on the boundary [Eq. (4)] was solved both numerically [Eq. (7)] and by using the approximated analytical expression [Eq. (8)]. The obtained solution allowed us to derive explicit formulae [Eq. (15)] for heat flux along the conductor for the case when the temperature difference is applied across the ends of the conductor for any diameter-to-length ratio.

The obtained results differ from the well-known results of the Knudsen regime for rarefied gas and the Casimir model for phonon heat flow in cylindrical conductors for two physical reasons. The first of them is that a definite temperature gradient is applied along the lateral wall of the conductor, and not a temperature difference across the ends only, as in our model. The second reason is the approximation of an infinitely long conductor in their models. Taking these two approximations into account, the general result [Eq. (16)] gives the well-known result of the Knudsen regime [Eq. (21)] for rarefied gas. Therefore, our obtained solution generalizes the formulae for the Knudsen limit to the case of a conductor of a finite length.

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Теплопередача в провідниках циліндричного перетину з дифузійним граничним розсіюванням

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Проведено теоретичне дослідження теплообмінних властивостей у тривимірних циліндричних провідниках скінченної довжини в балістичному режимі поширення фононів. Фононне випромінювання вважається радіаційним, а його взаємодія з боковою границею вважається повністю дифузійною. Основною метою дослідження є визначення профілю температури та особливостей його формування для узагальненого випадку провідника скінченної довжини. Отримано матричний чисельний розв'язок інтегрального рівняння для потоку енергії частинок та запропоновано наближений аналітичний розв'язок цього рівняння. Визначено тепловий потік і коефіцієнт теплопровідності та обговорено значну різницю між отриманими результатами та результатами загальноприйнятого формулювання в режимі Кнудсена та моделі Казимира.

Ключові слова: теплообмін, провідник, теплопровідність, балістичний режим поширення фононів, випромінювання фононів.